

Tunisia's Pathway for power sector decarbonization under clean ammonia target

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Executive Summary:

The OSeMOSYS tool using the clicSand interface has been used to develop three scenarios (BAU, RE and GAP) in order to evaluate the potential pathway for power sector decarbonization in Tunisia for the time horizon 2015 to 2070. The results indicate that renewable energy, particularly solar PV and onshore wind, will play a significant role in the future energy mix in terms of costs and CO₂ emission mitigation compared with the BAU scenario. The integration of green hydrogen for ammonia production to satisfy local market demand can be supplied by the power sector until 2060, then dedicated renewable power plants have to be implemented, which will need a robust roadmap and regulation framework.

1. Introduction

Since 2000, Tunisia has been dealing with a consistent deficit in its energy balance, as the energy demand continues to exceed the available supply. The country relies on fossil fuels, especially natural gas, of which over 50% is imported. To address these challenges and combat climate change, Tunisia is committed to addressing climate

change through both mitigation and adaptation efforts. This commitment was strengthened in 2015 when Tunisia submitted its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) to the UNFCCC, later updated in 2021. Tunisia aims to reduce its carbon intensity by 45% by 2030 compared to 2010 [1].

In this work, we will focus on the following two key pillars of Tunisia's low-carbon strategy:

- Diversifying the energy mix and increasing the share of renewables, to achieve 35% of total installed capacity from renewable sources by 2030.
- Integrating green hydrogen and its derivatives, primarily to meet local market demand, by prioritizing the production of green hydrogen for ammonia production to decarbonize the fertilizer industry and improve supply reliability. Currently, 100% of the ammonia is imported annually, with an estimated value of 250kt.

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the most optimized pathway for electricity generation for green hydrogen production in Tunisia and assess the impact on costs.

We propose the following research questions:

- What is the optimal electricity mix to achieve the national renewable energy integration target?
- What is the most cost-effective way to supply electricity for hydrogen production to meet the national demand for ammonia?

2. Methodology

In this study, the OSeMOSYS model using the ClicSand interface is used. OSeMOSYS is developed by the Royale Institute of Technology KTH and other stakeholders. It is a long-term optimization tool for planning energy investments. It computes the least cost energy supply options and investments to meet energy demands under some constraints. The model includes the current and potential electricity supply options from primary energy to final demand. The model covers the following electricity generation technologies for the modelling period 2015-2070 (See Figure 1):

- Conventional technologies:

- Open cycle gas turbines small sizes
- Combined cycle gas turbines
- Renewable technologies:
 - Onshore wind farms
 - Offshore wind farms
 - Solar photovoltaic power plants
 - Concentrating solar power plant
 - Hydropower plant
 - Biomass power plant
- Electricity import and export technologies

Figure 1: Tunisia Reference Energy System

The data on demand, existing capacities, and costs were collected from the official reports [2], [3], [4]. Also, we used the starter data kit to develop the baseline scenario [5]. The model was calibrated and then validated based on historical results trends.

Three main scenarios have been developed:

- Business As Usual Scenario (BAU): Fossil future scenario, no target on renewable technologies
- Renewable Energy scenario (RE): The Tunisian Solar plan target (Minimum installed capacity of 35% by 2030)
- Green Ammonia Production Scenario (GAP): The local ammonia demand from green hydrogen starting from 2030, with 20% growth between 2030 and 2050.

3. Results

Installed capacity (Capacity shares)

As shown in Figure 2, in 2022, the same capacity will be installed for all three scenarios (historical data reproduction), demonstrating the reliability of the results. In the BAU scenario: Conventional technologies are dominated until 2060 and then, we observed penetration of onshore wind and solar PV due to cost decreases throughout the time horizon of these technologies. However, RE scenario: The application of the Tunisian solar plan target has led to a significant increase in the share of renewable energies, dominated by solar Pv, followed by onshore wind. We also noticed the penetration of solar CSP, offshore wind and biomass power plants. For the GAP scenario: From 2060, the power sector will not be able to supply electricity for green hydrogen production. Solar-dedicated power plants will need to be implemented (See Appendix). In addition to that, we noticed that no electricity imports from 2030 in any of the three scenarios, demonstrating the future resiliency of the power supply.

Figure 2: Capacity shares from 2022 to 2070

Power generation

From 2030 to 2050 (Figure 3), the difference between the RE and GAP scenarios is small because the demand for green hydrogen for ammonia production represents only 2% of the total power demand. However, from 2060, additional electricity will need to be generated from dedicated solar technology. In addition, both BAU and RE scenarios show the same power generation because we consider only the power sector in our assumptions.

Figure 3: Power generation from 2022 to 2070

Costs evaluation

As depicted in Figure 4, the BAU scenario incurs the highest costs due to the increased variable costs associated with natural gas imports. This is followed by the GAP scenario, attributable to the new investment in hydrogen technology.

Emissions

The emissions (See Figure 5) have decreased significantly from BAU and RE scenarios, with no significant difference between RE and GAP. The integration of renewable energy will reduce the CO₂ emissions.

Figure 5: Emissions evolution

4. Discussion

Based on the modeling results, we have identified several implications crucial for advancing Tunisia's renewable energy landscape. Firstly, the Renewable Energy (RE) scenario indicates a significant increase in the share of renewables in the country's energy mix. This shift requires the Tunisian government to provide substantial support to the private sector to accelerate the adoption of renewable energy. Encouraging investments and offering incentives for renewable energy projects are essential strategies to drive this transition. Simplifying regulatory frameworks and ensuring a stable investment environment will further encourage the participation of private entities in the renewable energy sector. Furthermore, the integration of renewable energies and green hydrogen is expected to significantly reduce CO₂ emissions, aligning with Tunisia's climate targets and international commitments. Solar photovoltaic (PV) and onshore wind are identified as key technologies with considerable potential for the future, especially in the Tunisian context, where natural conditions favor these renewable resources. Additionally, the adoption of hybrid power plants, which combine

different renewable energy sources, presents a promising solution to address the intermittency issues associated with renewable energy, ensuring a more reliable and stable power supply. Looking at the year 2050, the electricity required for green hydrogen production to meet local ammonia demand can be efficiently generated from the power sector. Tunisia's potential as a green hydrogen exporter adds another dimension to its renewable energy strategy. To capitalize on this opportunity, the government must plan for the future by implementing dedicated renewable power plants for green hydrogen production. Although this may not be an immediate priority, it is essential that Tunisia positions itself strategically through the development of a clear and robust roadmap. Finally, further improvements to the model could be achieved by incorporating emissions data from various power technologies and enhancing the model to include the ammonia supply chain. Additionally, exploring other applications for green hydrogen will be crucial for maximizing its potential within Tunisia's energy landscape.

5. Conclusion

This study utilized the OSeMOSYS tool with the clicSand interface to model three scenarios—Business As Usual (BAU), Renewable Energy (RE), and Green Ammonia Production (GAP) to explore potential pathways for decarbonizing Tunisia's power sector from 2015 to 2070. The results emphasize the critical role of renewable energy, particularly solar PV and onshore wind, in reducing costs and CO₂ emissions. Additionally, the study highlights the importance of integrating green hydrogen production, especially for ammonia, as part of Tunisia's energy strategy.

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Appendices

Total Annual costs

Hydrogen production

